

KNOWLEDGE
WITHOUT
BOUNDARIES

eifl 2022
ANNUAL
REPORT

WHERE WE WORK

In 2022, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 37 countries and ran projects in an additional 16 countries where we do not have library consortia.

- **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.
- **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we work with libraries on specific projects.

WHERE WE WORK

EIFL works in collaboration with libraries in 53 developing and transition countries.

AFRICA Botswana, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Namibia, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe

ASIA PACIFIC Cambodia, China, Fiji, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Laos, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, Thailand, Uzbekistan

EUROPE Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Georgia, Hungary, Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine

LATIN AMERICA Chile, Colombia
MIDDLE EAST & NORTH AFRICA Palestine, Sudan, Syria.

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**OUR VISION IS A WORLD IN
WHICH ALL PEOPLE HAVE THE
KNOWLEDGE THEY NEED TO
ACHIEVE THEIR FULL POTENTIAL.**

Photo by Jjumba Martin

WHO WE ARE

EIFL (Electronic Information for Libraries) is an international not-for-profit organization that works with libraries in developing and transition countries to enable access to knowledge for education, learning, research and sustainable community development.

Our strategy has three main goals:

To advance a fair and sustainable transition from paywalled to open access content

Major achievements in 2022 -

- 14 agreements with publishers were in place enabling authors from EIFL partner countries to publish for free, or at reduced prices, in open access in 2,280 journals. 1,471 authors benefited from these agreements and they published 1,679 articles in open access. Savings in Article Processing Charges (APCs) for authors and their institutions in EIFL partner countries amounted to US\$2,350,506.
- Read & Publish agreements, in which researchers can access journals and also publish articles in open access without paying APCs: In 2022, Estonia, Fiji, Ghana, Latvia, Lithuania and Palestine signed up for the EIFL-negotiated agreement with Cambridge University Press, and Latvia and Slovenia joined the agreement with SAGE Publications.
- We provided advice to institutions that were developing open access policies. Seven institutions (in Armenia, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Moldova and Uganda) adopted policies mandating deposit of research output in open access repositories, and eight more open access policies (in Armenia, Botswana, Ghana, Kenya Kyrgyzstan and Lesotho) are under discussion by university administrations.

To support research, teaching and learning

Major achievements in 2022 -

- We helped libraries to provide remote access to licensed e-resources by negotiating with technology service providers. In 2022, 208 libraries subscribed to EIFL-negotiated remote access services.
- We advocated for national copyright law reform to encourage the adoption of modern copyright laws that maximize access to content:
 - Participated in copyright law review processes in Kenya, Kosovo, Namibia, Nigeria, South Africa and Uganda.
 - Contributed to ending the book famine for persons with print disabilities by supporting ratification and implementation of the Marrakesh Treaty in Armenia, Kenya, Ukraine and Vietnam.
- At the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), we supported a new proposal by the African Group for a work programme on copyright limitations and exceptions. Member states agreed on specific lines of action for preservation, research and cross-border uses.
- We advocated for creation and maintenance of open public infrastructures that enable the publication and sharing of research in open access journals and open repositories:
 - Contributed to adoption of national open science policies enabling open public infrastructures in Croatia, Estonia, Latvia, Romania, Slovenia and Ukraine, and draft policies that are now being discussed in three countries (Armenia, Botswana and Moldova) and at the Ethiopian Ministry of Agriculture.
 - EIFL support led 65 institutions, in Ethiopia, Georgia, Ghana and Kenya, to launch open access journal publishing platforms using Open Journal Systems software.
- EIFL support led to improvements in the quality of 98 open access journals and repositories.
- EIFL support led to the launch of eight new open access repositories in Democratic Republic of Congo and Ghana.
- EIFL coordinated the writing of DSpace 7 user documentation and hosted a DSpace 7 webinar.
- We contributed resources to the UNESCO Open Science Toolkit to support implementation of the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.
- To enhance open science and open research skills of librarians and researchers, we:
 - Hosted two train-the-trainer bootcamps for open science trainers.
 - Contributed to the development of 15 courses in Ukrainian on open science for Master's and PhD students, which received accreditation in four universities in Ukraine.
 - Supported the development of a handbook on open access in Kyrgyzstan that is being distributed to universities across the country.

To foster digital transformation of public library services

Major achievements in 2022 -

- We built digital literacy skills and advocated for improvements of ICT infrastructure in Uganda:

- With partners, we continued with our training-of-trainers programme for 27 public and community libraries. By the end of 2022, over 11,000 vulnerable people, mostly women and youth, had completed digital skills training, delivered by our trained librarians. The training programme attracted a donation of 10 computers from MTN Foundation Uganda for one of the participating libraries.
- Continued our relationship with the Uganda Communications Commission (UCC). In 2022, UCC provided 10 computers and internet connectivity to 10 public and community libraries.
- Produced a series of four microlearning videos for public librarians and public library trainers who deliver ICT training in their communities.
- We advocated at the Internet Governance Forum (IGF) for inclusion of public libraries in national ICT development plans. In 2022, within the framework of the IGF Dynamic Coalition of Public Access in Libraries, we released the final report of a study providing an overview of evidence of the impacts and benefits of public access to computers and the internet in libraries.
- We selected four libraries (in Colombia, Kenya, Lithuania and Serbia) for the EIFL Public Library Innovation Award for enabling learning through play. The award was supported by the LEGO Foundation.

DIRECTOR'S REPORT

Our year began with the shock of Russia's unprovoked attack on Ukraine. The war remained on our minds throughout the year, and we were seeking ways of supporting libraries and their users. We welcomed initiatives by publishers to open up their content to all Ukrainian institutions free of charge.

As the war intensified, the numbers of refugees grew. We were asked by libraries in Europe for advice on how to obtain accessible format reading materials in the Ukrainian language for refugees with print disabilities. We prepared an information sheet on how to use the Marrakesh Treaty to get such materials.

To help keep Ukrainian scholarly journals alive, we joined SUES - Supporting Ukrainian Editorial Staff - a coalition of organizations involved in scholarly communications. SUES raised enough money to support 45 journals, helping them with day-to-day activities. Journal editors were also interested in learning about best practices in academic journal publishing, and so we co-organized a series of webinars for them.

In February the Budapest Open Access Initiative, which coined the term open access, celebrated its 20th anniversary. EIFL was one of the original signatories to the initiative. We were happy to assist in the celebrations and identify priorities for the future.

In November the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, which provides an international framework for open science policy and practice, marked its first anniversary. The work of the EIFL Open Access Programme in advancing open science policies, open infrastructures and open science skills is featured in this report.

Commercial scholarly journals are transitioning to open access. While the transition is happening, we are continuing to negotiate with publishers for affordable access to e-resources and Article Processing Charges (APC) for publishing in open access. EIFL-negotiated access to journals, e-books and databases was well used in 2022, with almost seven million downloads of full-text articles, e-books and e-book chapters by scholars in our partner countries. Over 1,470 researchers took advantage of the waived or discounted APCs and published 1,679 articles with 12 publishers. However, in general APCs remain unaffordable, and we are concerned about this.

Thank you to everyone who helped to make our work possible - our partners, our funders, our board members and our staff. I hope you enjoy our report, and look forward to engaging with you again in 2023.

RIMA KUPRYTĖ, DIRECTOR OF EIFL

Photo by Augustinas Žukovas

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION DAY IN UKRAINE

A GLOBAL VISION FOR OPEN SCIENCE

EIFL's contribution to implementing the UNESCO
Recommendation on Open Science

“Through its expertise, networks and long-standing experience in promoting access to knowledge, EIFL has been an instrumental partner in developing the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science and is at the core of the global efforts focusing on its implementation.”

– ANA PERŠIĆ, SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION POLICY, NATURAL SCIENCES SECTOR, UNESCO

The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science - the first-ever international standard for open science - was formally adopted by UNESCO's 193 Member States on 23 November 2021.

EIFL participated in the development of the Recommendation through the UNESCO Global Open Science Partnership, which brought together open science stakeholders from across the world in an inclusive consultative process. Iryna Kuchma, EIFL Open Access Programme Manager, was one of 30 international experts appointed by UNESCO's Director-General to serve on the Advisory Committee that advised the global partnership and prepared a draft recommendation.

The Recommendation provides an international framework for open science policy and practice that recognizes regional and disciplinary differences, and takes into account academic freedom, gender-transformative approaches and the specific challenges faced in different countries.

It provides the first internationally agreed definition of open science, as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices, aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community (for example, indigenous knowledge-holders). A key aim of the Recommendation is to bridge the science, technology and innovation gaps between and within countries.

To realize its objectives, and to guide implementation, the Recommendation

proposes seven areas of action. As a member of the UNESCO Global Open Science Partnership, EIFL is committed to implementing the Recommendation, working with library consortia and other institutions in our partner countries.

In 2022, our work centred on three areas of action. Here we share some highlights of our contribution in 2022.

ACTION: DEVELOPING AN ENABLING POLICY ENVIRONMENT FOR OPEN SCIENCE

Open science policies are essential to foster a culture of open science nationally and within public and private institutions, and the Recommendation has sparked the revision of existing policies as well as the formulation of new ones.

In 2022, EIFL's contribution to national and institutional open science policy development processes bore fruit in several of our partner countries.

At the national level, our work has contributed to the adoption of a National Open Science Action Plan in Ukraine; completion of draft national science roadmaps in three countries (Armenia, Botswana and Moldova) and a draft policy for the Ethiopian Ministry of Agriculture.

In Ukraine, EIFL's Iryna Kuchma served on the National Open Science Working Group at the Ministry of Education and Science that developed the National Open Science Action Plan. Late in 2022, the Government of Ukraine approved the National Open Science Action Plan, and mandated all Ministries to ensure that it is implemented.

The Action Plan stipulates integration of open

science into all national science, research, education, technology and innovation policies, strategies and action plans, by 2025, and provides guidance to achieve this. The Action Plan encourages Ukrainian open access journals to register with the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), and allocates Government funding for a national research repository to be integrated with institutional repositories. Reforming research assessment and open science training are among the priorities for 2023.

In Botswana, EIFL's partner, the Botswana Libraries Consortium (BLC), played a central role in coordinating the drafting of a national open science policy. The chair of the BLC, and EIFL Country Coordinator, Naniki Mphakwane, is the Secretary of the Botswana Open Science Policy Working Group.

Developing the policy was a huge task, says Naniki.

“Most of Botswana's universities and research institutions, and government ministries, civil society and the private sector were represented on the Working Group. The task came towards the end of the year and we worked tirelessly to ensure that there would be a draft ready before the recess in December 2022. We succeeded, and the draft policy is ready for the Ministry of Communications, Knowledge, Science and Technology, which is leading the due process for consultations and adoption.”

If the process runs smoothly, Parliament will approve the policy in June 2023.

“It will be exciting to have an enabling policy that will be a driver of change. The policy promotes innovative processes for open science, by providing incentives - for example, rewards

for researchers who innovate, and support for scholars undertaking research using open science practices. We have proposed a budget for the implementation of the policy, including for actions like establishing infrastructure and capacity building of librarians and students.

“EIFL played a big role in the development of the draft policy through Iryna who constantly provided expertise and experience,” says Naniki.

In 2022 EIFL also contributed to the adoption of open science policies by seven institutions, in Armenia, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Côte d'Ivoire, Kenya and Uganda. One institution in Moldova updated its existing open access policy to include open science, and eight institutions, in Armenia, Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, Kyrgyzstan and Lesotho, have drafted policies in 2022 that are now being discussed by university managements.

ACTION: INVESTING IN OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURES AND SERVICES

In 2021 / 22 EIFL provided small grants to support projects to establish and improve open science infrastructures for sharing of research. The grants supported development of open journals publishing platforms and institutional repositories in eight partner countries: Armenia, DRC, Ethiopia, Georgia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho and Uganda.

The results have been far-reaching: 20 institutions in Georgia, 18 in Ghana, 17 in Kenya and 10 in Ethiopia - a total of 65 institutions - have launched national and institutional open access journal publishing platforms. Eight institutions - one in the DRC and seven in Ghana - have established open repositories. In addition, the funded projects

contributed to improved quality of services of almost 100 institutional open access journals and repositories.

All the projects had awareness-raising and capacity building components, with workshops and training that reached hundreds of people - institutional leadership and management, faculty and researchers, journal editorial staff and authors, librarians and IT teams. As a result, there is now greater buy-in for open science at leadership level, and the question of policies to govern and guide use of open science infrastructures is firmly on the agenda.

As a further contribution, we organized seven weekly webinars for African open access journal editors and publishers, with partners (ASSAf - Academy of Science South Africa; AJOL - African Journals Online; DOAJ; LIBSENSE and the University of Cape Town), and coordinated the writing of DSpace 7 user documentation for repository managers and administrators.

SOME EXAMPLES

In Ghana our partner, CARLIGH (the Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Ghana) has member institutions spread across the country. CARLIGH deployed technical teams to visit selected institutions to support installation of new repositories, to improve existing ones and to train library staff to populate repositories with research output. As a result, 16 institutions now have functioning OA repositories and are sharing their research.

CARLIGH also organized three regional open access journal management, editorial and technical workshops, reaching 240 journal managers and editors, authors, librarians and IT staff from 19 institutions. The project built capacity to install and manage Open Journal Systems (OJS) publishing platforms at 18 institutions. Most of the institutions have taken steps to install OJS and have begun publishing and hosting institutional journals.

“There is now greater enthusiasm for open science. Faculty and students are keen to deposit their articles and data in the new institutional repositories. And we have stronger

backing from university managements because they are more aware about how showcasing your research affects university rankings,” says Richard Bruce Lamptey, Librarian at the College of Science Library at Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST), and EIFL Country Coordinator in Ghana.

The CARLIGH technical teams are available to provide ongoing technical support to member institutions that have established new open science infrastructures.

In Kenya, our national partner, the Kenya Libraries and Information Services Consortium (KLISC), worked with member institutions that wanted to publish their print journals in open access online. KLISC set up OJS publishing platforms, and built editorial and technical capacity at 17 institutions in five regions of Kenya. Work has now begun on moving back issues of journals online and publishing current issues using OJS.

In Armenia we supported the National Library of Armenia (NLA) to create a new open access repository using the most up-to-date open repositories software, DSpace 7. The new repository is central to Armenia’s growing national open science infrastructure. By the end of 2022, NLA staff had moved 825 theses and dissertations to the new repository, and will continue with this work in 2023.

ACTION: INVESTING IN HUMAN RESOURCES, TRAINING, EDUCATION, DIGITAL LITERACY AND CAPACITY BUILDING FOR OPEN SCIENCE

EIFL is involved in several open science capacity building initiatives.

As chair of the OpenAIRE Training and Support Standing Committee, Iryna Kuchma contributed to building the OpenAIRE training platform for open science and co-designed open science support materials for Horizon Europe, the European Union’s key funding programme for research and innovation. Iryna also co-hosted two open science train-the-trainer bootcamps for 76 trainers.

EIFL is one of 11 partners taking part in the OPTIMA project, funded by the European education and training programme, Erasmus+. The OPTIMA project promotes openness and transparency in research in Ukraine by fostering open science practices and open peer review among early career researchers. The project has developed 15 open science courses in Ukrainian for Master’s and PhD students, and these have received accreditation in four project partner universities.

With support from EIFL, the American University of Central Asia (AUCA) in Kyrgyzstan organized and hosted open access training for university librarians and research offices from all regions of Kyrgyzstan. AUCA has also developed and shared a handbook on open access in Kyrgyz and Russian.

EIFL is contributing to the UNESCO Open Science Toolkit, with factsheets, guides and checklists to support implementation of the Recommendation.

We collaborated with the LIBSENSE community in developing the Checklist for universities on implementing the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.

We teamed up with OASPA (the Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association) to develop the Checklist for open access publishers on implementing the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. :

“We’re grateful to UNESCO for hosting the guidelines and also to EIFL’s Iryna Kuchma for working with OASPA on these and making the Checklist for open access publishers a really valuable and globally relevant resource,” said Claire Redhead, Executive Director of OASPA.

The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science is just one year old. As it goes into its second year we will continue to work with our partners to advance a global vision of open science.

The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science - EIFL’s contribution in 2022

OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES

- 6 - countries adopted national policies
- 4 - countries drafted national policies
- 8 - institutions adopted policies
- 8 - institutions drafted policies

OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURES

- 100+ - new journals published in open access
- 65 - institutions launched open access journal publishing platforms
- 8 - institutions launched new open access repositories
- 98+ - open access journals and repositories services improved

CAPACITY BUILDING FOR OPEN SCIENCE

- 3,500+ - people trained
- 146 - open science trainers trained

Thank you to the Open Society Foundations for supporting the EIFL Open Access Programme.

MEET THE PEOPLE

Using knowledge to change their lives
and the lives of others

AWA CISSÉ DIOUF

UNIVERSITY LIBRARIAN, UNIVERSITÉ CHEIKH ANTA DIOP SENEGAL

Awa Cissé Diouf, EIFL's Copyright Coordinator in Senegal, has been part of several EIFL delegations to meetings of the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), where EIFL campaigns for a global copyright framework that supports libraries and the people who use them. In 2022, Awa participated in the 42nd session of the WIPO Standing Committee on Copyright and Related Rights (SCCR/42). "Agreements at that meeting really inspired me with confidence. The main item was a proposal by the African Group for a work plan on limitations and exceptions. It contains concrete actions directly affecting libraries, including the development of a toolkit on preservation, and examination of the complex topic of cross-border uses of copyrighted works. These actions will be presented at SCCR in 2023," she says.

"When copyright exceptions differ from country to country, librarians are hindered from sending and receiving requested resources across borders. A WIPO agreement would help by encouraging countries to bring their national laws into alignment, making cross-border resource-sharing more possible globally." With support from EIFL, Awa also leads advocacy for copyright law reform in Senegal to promote the rights of libraries, education, research and people with disabilities.

"Senegal has no explicit exceptions for libraries. Our law is more about protecting rightsholders and commercial interests. It does not take into account the social aspects of access to knowledge and information. This has to change. To support our goal, we established a coalition of stakeholders to advocate for national reform, held a launch workshop with high-level government officials, and commissioned a review of Senegal's copyright law as a baseline for advocacy. The review will be published in 2023."

Photo: Emmanuel Berrod. © WIPO. This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International Licence <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>

"Over the years, I have learnt that with advocacy, you must be patient and optimistic. I am more optimistic than ever before that we are getting closer to creating a copyright environment in which libraries can support education and research without fear of copyright infringement and litigation."

– AWA CISSÉ DIOUF

KARMEN ŠTULAR SOTOŠEK

EXECUTIVE DIRECTOR, COSEC SLOVENIA

Karmen Štular Sotošek, EIFL's Country Coordinator in Slovenia, has been managing COSEC, EIFL's partner library consortium, for almost 20 years.

COSEC, which works within the framework of the National and University Library of Slovenia, has three overall goals: to save public money; to provide digital content for its network of 46 university, faculty, research and regional libraries, and to create a sustainable ecosystem for open access publishing.

"EIFL has played an important role in helping us to achieve our goals," says Karmen.

Karmen is part of the COSEC team that negotiates agreements with publishers for affordable licensed access to scholarly e-resources for member institutions. "We base our agreements on the EIFL model," says Karmen.

In 2022 COSEC negotiated agreements for access to 66 e-resources for universities, 22 for special research organizations and eight for public libraries. These e-resources include scholarly journals, databases and e-books.

"Savings in public money have been substantial. We estimate that on average, we are saving more than 50% in subscription fees," says Karmen.

In the context of Slovenia's open science policies and guided by EIFL's principles for negotiations, COSEC also enters into Read & Publish (R&P) agreements with publishers. These provide access to scholarly journals while at the same time allowing authors to publish articles in open access without having to pay Article Processing Charges (APCs). In 2022, COSEC had six R&P agreements providing authors with the opportunity to publish for free in 4,637 e-journals, resulting in a significant increase in the number of open access articles in hybrid journals.

"Thanks to these agreements, authors published 119 articles in open access in hybrid journals of these six publishers in 2022, compared with just 13 in 2019 before the R&P agreements."

Photo by Maj Blatnik (NUK)

"Read & Publish agreements are helping authors and institutions gradually to tip the balance of publishing output to open access, by making the publishing process easier and more financially viable."

– KARMEN ŠTULAR SOTOŠEK

DR GITAU NJOROGE

CHIEF UNIVERSITY LIBRARIAN, KENYATTA UNIVERSITY KENYA

Open access journal publishing in Kenya is steadily increasing as a result of a project that was implemented by the Kenya Library and Information Services Consortium (KLISC) in 2022, with support from EIFL.

Before the project, only three KLISC member universities had active online open access journals, says Dr Gitau Njoroge, who is EIFL's Open Access Coordinator in Kenya. "About 20 of our member institutions were publishing print journals and we targeted those that wanted to publish their journals online.

"The key challenge was to convince university managements that high quality open access journals could increase visibility of research output and raise university profiles. We achieved this by ensuring that senior staff participated in awareness-raising and training workshops, which we organized in five regions of Kenya.

"We trained editorial boards, researchers, ICT staff and librarians in open access publishing. We set up Open Journal Systems (OJS) platforms for hosting online journals at 17 institutions. We trained technical staff to customize and manage the platforms. In addition, we spoke about meeting quality standards for indexing in directories like the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). And we stressed the importance of policies to ensure adherence to best practices."

As a result, the number of open access journals being published is steadily increasing. Some universities such as Meru, Rongo, Strathmore, Kambanga and Kirinyaga have published the latest issues of their journals online, and other institutions have also uploaded back issues.

"There is now a new enthusiasm for open access publishing and a 'can-do' attitude. We will continue to build on this through follow-up workshops to make sure that publishing schedules and quality standards are maintained," says Dr Njoroge.

"KLISC and EIFL have together built a strong base for increasing and improving open access journal publishing in Kenya for wider research accessibility and discoverability."

– DR GITAU NJOROGE

PHIONA NAFUNA

DOCUMENTOR OF COMMUNITY LIFE FOR A TELEVISION STATION UGANDA

“My first experience of using a computer was when the library training started,” says Phiona Nafuna, a young mother living in Nkoma Village near the town of Mbale in Eastern Uganda.

The eldest of four children, Phiona left school early. “My three young brothers were still going to school, and my mum could not afford my school fees,” she explains.

One day, a friend told Phiona about free digital skills classes being offered by Mbale Public Library. Mbale is one of 27 public and community libraries in Uganda taking part in a project implemented by EIFL and partners, National Library of Uganda, Maendeleo Foundation and Peer 2 Peer University. The project builds the capacity of libraries to provide digital skills training in their communities, and connects learners to free online courses in entrepreneurial, craft-making, technical and other useful skills.

“I learnt Word, PowerPoint, writing and sending emails, and using the internet,” says Phiona. “I started applying for work, and was called to a job interview by Know Your City TV.

“They asked if I have a certificate for my computer skills. I produced the certificate that the library awarded me - and I have got the job! I am happy to be able to support my daughter, who is aged two, and to help my mother.”

Phiona also has a strong community spirit. Every Saturday, a women's group meets at the library to learn new practical skills. Using YouTube courses, the women have learnt how to make vaseline, liquid soap, paper bags and other crafts. As a volunteer Phiona helps the women to make and sell their produce.

Photo by Jjumba Martin

“Women and young people should get involved in every activity offered through these digital skills courses offered by the library for a better and brighter future.”

– PHIONA NAFUNA

OUR NETWORK

EIFL partner library consortia nominate coordinators who serve as the main point of contact between EIFL's Programmes and their consortium. In their countries, they lead and facilitate activities initiated by EIFL, and have been central to our success and achievements over the years.

We would like to thank all our Country Coordinators, Licensing Coordinators, Open Access Coordinators and Copyright Coordinators for their enthusiasm and hard work in 2022.

ALBANIA

Consortium of Albanian Libraries

Country Coordinator: Albana Velianj
Licensing Coordinators: Renata Bardhi and Mirlona Buzo
Open Access Coordinator: Renata Bardhi

ARMENIA

Digital Library Association of Armenia (DLAA)

Country Coordinator: Anna Chulyan
Licensing Coordinators: Tatevik Tamazyan
Copyright Coordinator: Hasmik Galstyan
Open Access Coordinator: Tigran Zakaryan

AZERBAIJAN

Azerbaijan Library and Information Consortium for Availability of Electronic Information (AzLIC)

Country Coordinator: Jamila Yusifova and Iltifat Ibrahimov
Licensing Coordinator: Iltifat Ibrahimov

BOTSWANA

Botswana Libraries Consortium (BLC)

Country & Licensing: Coordinator: Naniki Maphakwane
Copyright Coordinator: Khutsafalo Kadimo
Open Access Coordinator: Poloko Ntokwane

CHINA

Library Network of the Chinese Academy of Sciences

Country Coordinator: Xiwen Liu
Open Access & Copyright Coordinator: Kunhua Zhao

CONGO

Consortium des Bibliothèques Académiques du Congo (COBAC)

Country Coordinator: Eliezer Mwangane
Licensing Coordinator: Jean Baptiste Unen

CÔTE D'IVOIRE

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur de Côte d'Ivoire (COBES-CI)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Cécile Coulibaly
Copyright Coordinator: Ahou Marie-Claire Allou Ouffouet
Open Access Coordinator: Adjoh Hortense Kakpo Epse Outtara

ESTONIA

Consortium of Estonian Libraries Network (ELNET)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Marika Meltsas
Copyright Coordinator: Karmen Linask
Open Access Coordinator: Elena Sipria-Mironov

ETHIOPIA

Consortium of Ethiopian Academic and Research Libraries (CEARL)

Country Coordinator: Derib Erget Mamuye (until July); Girma Aweke (from July)
Copyright Coordinator: Ato Yoseph Bizuneh
Licensing Coordinator: Bedassa Motuma Beyene
Open Access Coordinator: Getnet Lemma

FIJI

Fiji Library Consortium

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Udaya Shukla

GEORGIA

Georgian Integrated Library Information System Consortium (GILISC) 2017

Country, Open Access & Copyright Coordinator: Nino Pavliashvili
Licensing Coordinator: Marika Zhorzholiani

GHANA

Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Ghana (CARLIGH)

Country Coordinator: Richard Bruce Lamptey
Copyright Coordinator: Teresa Adu
Licensing Coordinator: Mac Anthony Cobblah
Open Access Coordinator: Donyina Fokuo and Nana Tuhufu Quagraine

KENYA

Kenya Libraries and Information Services Consortium (KLISC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Arnold Mwanzu
Copyright Coordinator: Janegrace Kinyanjui
Open Access Coordinator: George Njoroge

KOSOVO

Consortium of Electronic Libraries in Kosovo (CELK)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Bukurije Haliti

KYRGYZSTAN

Kyrgyzstan Library Information Consortium (KLIC)

Country Coordinator: Jyldyz Bekbalaeva
Licensing Coordinator: Tolgonai Kozhokanova

LAOS

Laos Library and Information Consortium (LALIC)

Country, Copyright & Licensing Coordinator: Sypha Phongsavath
Open Access Coordinator: Sisavanh Linsavath

LATVIA

Culture Information Systems Centre

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Agrita Sagalajeva
Copyright Coordinator: Inta Mikluna

LESOTHO

Lesotho Library Consortium (LELICO)

Country Coordinator: Buhle Mbambo-Thata
Copyright Coordinator: Pontso Nkuebe
Licensing Coordinator: Tahleho Tseole
Open Access Coordinator: Matseliso Kabeli

LITHUANIA

Lithuanian Research Library Consortium (LMBA)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Ausra Vaskeviciene (until July); Jevgenija Sevcova (from July)
Copyright Coordinator: Janina Marcinkeviciene
Open Access Coordinator: Gintare Tautkeviciene

MALAWI

Malawi Library and Information Consortium (MALICO)

Country Coordinator: Patrick Mapulanga (from March)
Licensing Coordinator: Trevor Namondwe
Copyright Coordinator: Blessings Katuma (from March)
Open Access Coordinator: Fiskani Ngwira (until September); Chifundo Chipendo (from September)

MALDIVES

(No name – under development)

Country Coordinator: Aminath Shiuna (until September); Zulhana Adam (from September)
Licensing Coordinator: Aminath Shiuna (until September); Majidha Ali (from September)

MOLDOVA

Electronic Resources for Moldova (REM)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Elena Tudor Railean
Copyright Coordinator: Mariana Harjevschi
Open Access Coordinator: Natalia Cheradi

NAMIBIA

Namibia Library Consortium (NALICO)

Country & Copyright Coordinator: Victoria Isaacks
Licensing Coordinator: Namutenya Hamwaalwa

NEPAL

Nepal Library and Information Consortium (NeLIC)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Jagadish Aryal

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonian e-Libraries (MEL)

Country, Licensing & Copyright Coordinator: Miodrag Dadasovic
Open Access Coordinator: Rozita Petrinska Labudovikj (from July)

PALESTINE

Palestinian Library and Information Consortium (PALICO)

Country Coordinators: Diana Sayej Naser; Rami Alhindawi for Gaza
Licensing Coordinator: Mohammad Abu Hamdieh
Open Access Coordinator: Asad Tom

SENEGAL

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur du Sénégal (COBESS)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Youssoupha Gueye (until May); Mandiaye Ndiaye (from May)
Copyright Coordinator: Awa Diouf Cisse
Open Access Coordinator: Mandiaye Ndiaye (until August); Djibril Diallo, Abdoulaye Gueye, Mangaty Sakho (from August)

SERBIA

Serbian Library Consortium for Coordinated Acquisition (KoBSON)

Country Coordinator: Tatjana Timotijevic
Licensing Coordinators: Tatjana Timotijevic and Boris Denadic
Copyright Coordinator: Dragana Milunovic
Open Access Coordinator: Milica Sevkusic

SLOVENIA

Consortium of Slovene Electronic Collections (COSEC)

Country Coordinator: Karmen Stular Sotosek
Licensing Coordinator: Herman Erculj
Open Access Coordinator: Alenka Kavcic-Colic

SUDAN

Sudanese Academic Libraries Consortium (SALC)

Country Coordinator: Iman Abdelrahman
Copyright & Licensing Coordinator: Abdelaziz Gabir
Open Access Coordinator: Rania M. Hassan Baleela

TANZANIA

Consortium of Tanzania Universities and Research Libraries (COTUL)

Country & Open Access Coordinator: Paul Samwel Muneja
Licensing Coordinator: Cyrill Ndekakao

THAILAND

Electronic Information for Libraries in Thailand (eifl-Thailand)

Country, Copyright and Licensing Coordinator: Soeythip Sukul
Open Access Coordinator: Adisak Sukul

UGANDA

Consortium of Uganda University Libraries (CUUL)

Country Coordinator: David Bukenya
Copyright Coordinator: Eric Haumba
Licensing Coordinator: Drake Tamale
Open Access Coordinator: Hassan Ssenangooba

UKRAINE

Association 'Informatio-Consortium'

Country, Copyright, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Oleksii Vasyliiev

UZBEKISTAN

EIFL Uzbekistan Consortium

Country Coordinator: Gulrukh Iskandarova
Licensing Coordinator: Alisher Kattabekov
Open Access Coordinator: Maksim Savochkin

ZAMBIA

Zambia Library Consortium (ZALICO)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Eness Chitumbo
Copyright Coordinator: Benson Njobvu
Open Access Coordinator: Pilate Chewe

ZIMBABWE

Zimbabwe University Libraries Consortium (ZULC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Sarlomie Zinyemba
Open Access Coordinator: Plaxedes Chaitezvi (until March); Blessing Chiparausha (from March)
Copyright Coordinator: Rosemary Maturure

OUR TEAM

The EIFL team met in-person in Vilnius, Lithuania, in June 2022, for the first time after two years of online meetings during the COVID-19 pandemic. From left: Ugnė Lipeikaitė, Rima Kuprytė, Edvaldas Baltrūnas, Teresa Hackett, Jean Fairbairn, Ramunė Petuchovaitė, Iryna Kuchma, Jevgenija Ševcova, Lorraine Estelle, Andrius Kriščiūnas and Louise Stoddard.

STAFF

Andrius Kriščiūnas, Finance Manager

Dick Kawooya, Coordinator of Copyright Advocacy in Africa, Right to Research Project

Edvaldas Baltrūnas, Public Library Innovation Programme Coordinator

Iryna Kuchma, Open Access Programme Manager

Jean Fairbairn, Communications Manager, Website and Publications

Jevgenija Ševcova, Programmes and Events Coordinator

Lorraine Estelle, Licensing Programme Manager

Louise Stoddard, Communications Manager

Milica Ševkušić, Open Access Programme, Project Coordinator (from May)

Ramunė Petuchovaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Manager

Rima Kuprytė, Director

Susan Schnuer, Public Library Innovation Programme Capacity Building Manager (until April)

Teresa Hackett, Copyright and Libraries Programme Manager

Ugnė Lipeikaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Impact Manager

MANAGEMENT BOARD

Emilija Banionytė, Chairperson, Vilnius County Adomas Mickevičius Public Library, Lithuania

Colleen Campbell, Max Planck Digital Library, Max Planck Society, Germany

Adam Hyde, Founder of Coko, Book Sprints, Paged.js, Open Publishing Awards and the Open Publishing Fest

Jyldyz Bekbalaeva, American University of Central Asia, Kyrgyzstan

Joel Sam, African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AFLIA), Ghana

FINANCIAL REPORT

EIFL INCOME AND EXPENDITURE 2022

INCOME	€	%
• Programme income	2,588,906	73.5 %
• Participation fees	487,477	13.8 %
• General Support	443,917	12.6 %
• Sponsorship, interest and other income	1,828	0.1 %

Total **3,522,128**

EXPENDITURE	€	%
• Programme delivery	764,795	85.3 %
• Personnel & contracted expenses	105,255	11.7 %
• Operating expenses	26,897	3.0 %

Total **896,947**

COMMITTED EXPENDITURE FOR 2023–2026 PROGRAMME DELIVERY **2,610,530**

CONTINUITY RESERVE **269,531**

OUR FUNDERS

ORGANIZATIONS

We would like to thank the following organizations for their generous support for our work in 2022:

- Arcadia Fund through the American University / Washington College of Law, and the Creative Commons Corporation
- Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation
- European Commission Erasmus+ Programme through Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine
- European Commission Horizon 2020 Framework Programme through OpenAIRE AMKE
- European Commission Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)
- LEGO Foundation
- Open Society Foundations
- University of Luxembourg (UNILU)
- Wehubit Programme (implemented by the Belgian development agency, Enabel)

INDIVIDUALS

Thank you to all the individuals who contributed to our campaign to raise funds through GlobalGiving for our 'Digital skills to empower women & youth in Uganda' project.

EVENTS

In 2022, EIFL organized, supported or took part in 124 events, workshops and conferences about issues that affect access to knowledge.

JANUARY

- Wehubit Knowledge Exchange Network meeting (Online)
- Eko-Konnect Users Conference (Online)
- Workshop to design EOSC training programme (Online)
- Training the Trainers workshop for Uganda public librarians (Kampala, Uganda)

FEBRUARY

- Diamond OA to Research Publications Workshop (Online)
- Webinar: The New EU Copyright Exceptions – A Model for the World? (Online)
- Paris Open Science European Conference (Paris, France, and Online)
- Webinar on Fair Dealing in Kenya (Online)
- Webinar: Introduction to DOAJ (Online)
- Meeting of EIFL-PLIP African public library trainers on open online learning resources for librarians (Online)
- Webinar: OA journals editorial processes & business models (Online)
- Two mobile digital literacy camps for community (Kasese, Uganda)
- Open Climate Community Call (Online)
- OJS & open science workshop for Kenyan universities (Nairobi, Kenya)
- Webinar: Copyright, licensing in OA journals (Online)
- Fair Dealing Coffee Morning. The Challenge of Using Copyright Exceptions for Global Online Teaching (Online)

MARCH

- Webinar on AI/TDM/Big Data in Kenya (Online)
- Webinar: OA journals best practices (Online)
- APAN53 Conference (Dhaka, Bangladesh, and Online)

- Webinar: OA journal indexing, other publishing platforms (Online)
- Webinar: Policy into Action: the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science under the spotlight – actions for publishing (Online)
- Webinar: Addressing predatory publishing (Online)
- Mobile digital literacy camp for community (Zigoti, Uganda)
- Webinar: Quality assessment for OA (Online)
- BOAI 20th Anniversary Webcast (Online)

APRIL

- Webinar: Get ready for WIPO! (Online)
- Mobile digital literacy camp for community (Mbale, Uganda)
- Meeting of EIFL-PLIP African public library trainers on the Digital Enquirer Kit (Online)
- The Right to Research in International Copyright Law. International Law Review Symposium (Washington DC, United States)
- EIFL-PLIP thematic workshop at WSIS Forum 2022 (Online)
- Mobile digital literacy camp for community (Tororo, Uganda)
- WACREN 2022 Conference (Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire, and Online)
- EOSC Provider Days (Online)
- Workshop: Proposed WIPO Copyright Limitations and Exceptions Work Programme and Broadcasting Treaty (Online)
- UNESCO Open Science Partnership meeting (Online)
- OA publishing workshop at Meru University of Science and Technology (Meru, Kenya, and Online)

- Panel discussion, IFLA session at WSIS Forum 2022: Innovation in Shared and Public Access for Digital Inclusion (Online)

MAY

- Mobile digital literacy camp for community (Wakiso District, Uganda)
- NI4OS-Europe event in Moldova (Online)
- WIPO Information Session on the Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Copyright Ecosystem (Geneva, Switzerland)
- WIPO Copyright Committee (42nd session) (Geneva, Switzerland)
- Forum on OA publishing for Rift Valley universities (Eldoret, Kenya, and Online)
- Meeting of the UNESCO Working Group on Open Science Capacity Building (Online)
- COAR Annual Meeting (Madrid, Spain, and Online)
- Young African Library Innovators study tour to Romania (Bucharest and other locations, Romania)
- UKSG 45th Annual Conference and Exhibition (Telford, United Kingdom)

JUNE

- Webinar: Rights Retention (Online)
- Occupy Library 2022 conference (Bucharest, Romania, and Online)
- OpenAIRE train-the-trainer bootcamp (Online)
- Seminar on open access for Kyrgyz universities (Bishkek, Kyrgyzstan, and Online)
- Webinar: Horizon Europe open science requirements in practice (Online)
- Meeting of EIFL-PLIP African public library trainers on short-form and micro-training methods (Online)

- 2022 TWAS Research Grant Webinar (Online)
- OJS workshop for central Kenya universities (Embu, Kenya)
- Train-the-Trainers workshop for Uganda public librarians (Kampala, Uganda)
- Webinar: OA publishing in public health (Online)
- Wehubit knowledge exchange network meeting (Online)

JULY

- EOSC Future Consortium meeting (Athens, Greece)
- WIPO Assemblies 2022 (Geneva, Switzerland)
- EuroScience Open Forum 2022 Katowice (Katowice, Poland, and Online)
- OJS workshop for the Western and Nyanza region Kenya universities (Rongo, Kenya, and Online)
- Ebooks – where are we heading? IFLA WLIC 2022 Satellite Meeting (Dublin, Ireland)
- FORCE11 Scholarly Communications Institute (FSCI) 2022 online training (Online)
- Webinar: Depositing Author Accepted Manuscripts in Institutional Repositories (Online)
- IFLA World Library and Information Congress 2022 (Dublin, Ireland)
- IFLA Book Launch: Navigating Copyright for Libraries (Dublin, Ireland)

AUGUST

- Webinar: Institutional Repository Assessment in Asia (Online)
- Webinar: Indexing journals in DOAJ - Ukraine (Online)
- Webinar: Copyright and licensing - Ukraine (Online)

- Meeting of EIFL-PLIP African public library trainers on Online learning (Online)
- Mobile digital literacy camp for community (Bundibugyo, Uganda)
- APAN54 Conference (Jinan, China, and Online)
- International Training Workshop on Open Science and SDGs (Online)

SEPTEMBER

- LEGO 'Build a World of Play' event for libraries (Online)
- National Research Repository Planning Workshop in Zambia (Lusaka, Zambia, and Online)
- OA Journal Publishing Policy Formulation, Adoption and Implementation Workshop (Kilifi, Kenya, and Online)
- University of Maribor Open Science Summer School (Maribor, Slovenia)
- ALPSP Annual Conference and Awards (Manchester, United Kingdom)
- Diamond Open Access Conference (Zadar, Croatia, and Online)
- Knowledge sharing meeting for Uganda public libraries (Kampala, Uganda)
- 3rd OA Specialist Workshop of China (Online)
- WIPO Draft Preservation Toolkit Stakeholder Consultation (Geneva, Switzerland)
- Heritage Preservation for a Sustainable Future conference (Yerevan, Armenia)

OCTOBER

- Webinar and demonstration - DSpace 7 (Online)
- Webinar: Open science policies in Francophone Africa (Online)
- Open Science Day, Slovenia (Ljubljana, Slovenia)
- Africa United as Never Before: the AfCFTA, Development, Industrialisation, and Value Chains lecture (Ottawa, Canada and Online)
- Mobile digital literacy camp for community (Mukono, Uganda)
- Meeting of EIFL-PLIP African public library trainers on investigating misinformation (Online)

- 2022 EIFL General Assembly (Online)
- Open Access Week (Online)
- FAIR Convergence Symposium (Leiden, The Netherlands, and Online)
- E-library training for Faculty of Law and Political Sciences at the National University of Laos (Online)
- OA Week celebration in Zimbabwe (Online)
- #OSICU2022 conference (Online)
- OJS training for the Kenya National Commission for UNESCO multi-disciplinary journal (Nairobi, Kenya, and Online)

NOVEMBER

- ISMTE Global Event (Online)
- Scholarly publishing in Serbia meeting (Belgrade, Serbia)
- Open Science Days IV, Serbia (Belgrade, Serbia)
- Uganda Internet Governance Forum 2022 (Kampala, Uganda, and Online)
- Service Documentation for EOSC Providers Workshop: Describing your service for onboarding (Online)
- Webinar: Fostering diversity and inclusion in scholarly communications (Online)
- EOSC Symposium 2022 (Prague, Czech Republic, and Online)
- Train-the-Trainers workshop for Uganda public librarians (Kampala, Uganda)
- UKSG November Conference (Online)
- OpenAIRE project information session - DIAMAS (Online)
- Global Equity in Open Access Publishing workshop (Online)
- EOSC Train-the-Trainer course (Online)
- EMEA ICOLC Fall Conference (Online)
- E-library training for Faculty of Law and Political Sciences at the National University of Laos (Online)
- Botswana Open Science Symposium (Gaborone, Botswana, and Online)
- UbuntuNet-Connect conference (Gaborone, Botswana, and Online)

- Internet Governance Forum (IGF) 2022 (Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, and Online)
- Webinar: Engaging meaningfully in WIPO: does it matter for librarians in Sub-Saharan Africa? (Online)

DECEMBER

- MINERVA project conference (Chişinău, Moldova, Republic of)
- Webinar on JSTOR evidence-based acquisition of books model (Online)
- OpenAIRE train-the-trainer bootcamp (Online)
- Meeting of EIFL-PLIP African public library trainers on building partnerships (Online)
- The Open Science Day (Cape Town, South Africa)
- Mobile digital literacy camp for community (Namayumba Village, Wakiso District, Uganda)
- Wehubit Knowledge Exchange Network meeting (Brussels, Belgium)
- South Centre-African Union Workshop on WIPO issues (Geneva, Switzerland)
- Webinar: Reforming research assessment in Ukraine (Online)

KEY

- Training, workshops and events organized and/or supported by EIFL
- Presentations given by EIFL staff or partners
- Conferences and events attended by EIFL staff

OUR PARTNERS

EIFL has built relationships with a wide range of organizations to make knowledge more accessible. In 2022, we worked with the following partners:

- Access to Knowledge (A2K) Coalition
- African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AfLIA)
- American University Washington College of Law (AUWCL)
- Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN)
- Association of Lithuanian Municipal Public Libraries
- Bioline International
- Black Stripe Foundation
- Center for International Property and Information Technology Law (CIPIIT), Strathmore University
- Citizen's Services & Libraries, City of Aarhus, Denmark
- Coalition Publi.ca
- Coalition S
- CODATA
- Coko Foundation
- Cologne City Library
- COMMUNIA Association
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)
- Copyright for Creativity
- Corporación Innovarte
- Coventry University
- Creative Commons
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- DSpace Community Advisory Team (DCAT), DuraSpace
- Education International
- EOSC Association
- Fundación Karisma
- GÉANT
- German Library Association
- Gigabit Library Network (GLN)
- Ghana Library Authority
- Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS)
- Google Scholar
- Harvard Open Access Project (HOAP)
- HIFA2020: Healthcare Information For All by 2020
- International Coalition of Library Consortia (ICOLC)
- International Council of Museums (ICOM)
- International Council on Archives (ICA)
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA)
- International Union for Conservation of Nature
- Libraries Development, Local Government Management Agency Ireland
- Kenya National Library Service
- Knowledge Ecology International (KEI)
- Library Copyright Alliance (LCA)
- LIBSENSE
- Maendeleo Foundation
- Namibia Library and Archives Service
- National Institute of Informatics of Japan
- National Library of Uganda
- Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (NDLTD)
- OpenAIRE AMKE
- Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association (OASPA)
- ORCID
- Open Society University Network (OSUN)
- OA2020
- Peer 2 Peer University
- Progress Foundation
- Public Knowledge Project (PKP)
- ReCreate South Africa
- South Centre
- SPARC
- SPARC Europe
- SUES (Supporting Ukrainian Editorial Staff) Coalition
- Tactical Tech
- The International Relations Round Table (IRRT), American Library Association
- The Library and Information Association of Zambia (LIAZ)
- The World Academy of Sciences (TWAS)
- UbuntuNet Alliance
- UKSG
- UNESCO
- West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)
- Wikimedia Deutschland
- Wildlife Conservation Society
- World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)
- Zambia Library Servicew

KEY

- EIFL is a founding member/signatory
- EIFL is a member
- EIFL staff are board or committee members
- Official relations (including MoU)
- Working relationship

In addition, EIFL collaborated with 82 partners through European Commission-funded projects: Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS); European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Future; Open Practices, Transparency and Integrity for Modern Academia (OPTIMA), and Strengthening Research Management and Open Science Capacities of HEIs in Moldova and Armenia (Minerva).

WHERE WE WORK

In 2022, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 38 countries and ran projects in an additional 16 countries where we do not have library consortia.

- **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.
- **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we work with libraries on specific projects.

STAY CONNECTED

[eifl.net](https://www.eifl.net)

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[eifl-net](https://www.eifl.net)

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